

I am not a chicken farmer

Mark Parry

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845306>

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How might we better understand academics and ourselves? On a warm day in the mid 1990s, I visited a chicken farm near Gosford. I was researching and writing an agriculture module and was there to consult with the farmer about his birds and the hidden layers of the farm infrastructure. I brought along a camera and audio recorder.

This presentation poetically explores co-designing with university academics and other subject matter experts (SMEs) by reflecting on that large part of the “educational technology iceberg” that's usually hidden and underwater. Those faint pencil-mark discussions, negotiations, and planning sessions are eventually erased and removed, rendered invisible when the final, sparkling learning resource is delivered. A central cog in the machine exists somewhere in the middle, a professional staff member with a job to do. Those specific and often complicated professional interactions about aligning content to assessments, the critical review of existing assets, and the sequencing of content and activities with pedagogy that are crucial to the role are usually rendered invisible as the course is delivered to learners.

I've been a multimedia producer, instructional designer, academic developer, learning designer, and learning technologist. I am not a chicken farmer. Drawn from professional experiences of more than 30 years as an educational developer working across various educational sectors, including university and higher education, this spoken word presentation explores a central yet often overlooked role of learning technologists in higher education and beyond.

My presentation

(11 mins)

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Video transcript for **I am not a chicken farmer: A learning designer's reflections on co-designing with academics** [<https://youtu.be/OV8vfgIwK9M?si=6uRjOnMyvN2wDZjZ>]

Hello, my name is Mark Parry. This presentation will take just over ten minutes. It reflects on the hidden aspects of co-designing with academics and Subject Matter Experts (SMEs), much like the submerged part of an educational technology iceberg. The erasures of planning, alignment of content with assessments, and the behind-the-scenes work of learning designers often go unnoticed when the final resource is delivered.

Visibility

Learning design, when done well, is invisible. My career began in 1990 in education, teaching science to high school students. As a teacher, I was central and visible, but when I transitioned to educational resource development in the 90s, my role became more behind-the-scenes. One of my first SMEs was a chicken farmer. Although my role shifted, I was still central to the production process, collaborating with talented technical and creative teams. These projects earned industry awards, though many are now outdated relics of the past.

Despite the invisibility of learning design in the final resource, the actual job role was respected and visible within the teams I worked with. As one screen designer put it, “We all make you look good.” This was a collaborative truth that resonated. I made sure not to take team members for granted.

Collaboration

Educational resources are team efforts, with screen designers, illustrators, coders, audio engineers, and SMEs all playing vital roles. My job appeals to my curiosity and love of learning. Over the years, I've learned from SMEs across various fields: chefs, hairdressers, lawyers, chicken farmers,

firefighters, accountants, anthropologists, scientists, film makers, school principals, board members, doctors—each providing expertise we transformed into educational materials.

However, collaboration isn't always smooth. Some SMEs and educational leaders welcome co-design, while others resist it, viewing learning designers as intruders or threats. I've experienced a range of interactions, both cooperative and adversarial. It all comes down to how the role of learning design is perceived.

Change

I've evolved from a classroom teacher to a learning designer working across educational sectors, from teaching kindergarten to postgraduates to corporate. I've worked as a part-time casual, contract casual, permanent full time, freelance external contractor, and volunteer. I've worked for about ten Australian universities, as an academic and as professional staff and also as a freelancer. Sometimes concurrently. I like being between worlds. I've contributed to dozens of higher educational research projects, especially media-based dissemination of findings, but I'm not a researcher. I describe myself as a practitioner. Apart from higher education, I've also worked in schools, colleges, government agencies, peak bodies, non-profits, corporate, and community organisations. Change is a constant. I love variety. I like being the teacher at the front of the room, but ...

I also like the behind-the-scenes nature of being a learning designer. This is a visual motif of what it's like being behind-the-scenes.

In the post-pandemic era, the role of learning designers has gained further recognition, especially in higher education and corporate training. However, I've often observed that learning design is often misunderstood, especially in systems where the role is reduced to a technical support function or ignored entirely. On top of this, polite, yet controlling behaviour, professional silos and gatekeeping are all problems.

As a recognised job role, learning design is better known now than in 1995, but there's still a way to go.

The shadow side of systems

In my own story as a learning designer, my fundamental aims have always been about trust, collaboration, and co-design to produce high quality learning resources. I like to make my SME look good. But there have been obstacles in my path: mostly SMEs, supervisors, and other leaders who don't seem to get it. Now, either they don't know any better, which is a problem, or – for other reasons – make terrible, short-sighted decisions. Which is also a problem. In well-designed systems, learning designers are acknowledged and supported. But in dysfunctional systems, we're often rendered invisible, treated as IT support or administrative staff. This misunderstanding leads to a lack of collaboration and respect, where SMEs (and leaders) may resist pedagogical and technical advice or avoid engaging with learning design altogether. Worse still, some of these leaders have had limited professional experience in learning, teaching and education.

A bit of an aside about gatekeeping, which is, in everyday language when someone controls or limits access to information, resources, or opportunities that others need. It's like when one person

holds the keys to a door and decides who gets to come in or stay out. This can make things harder for others who want to contribute or move forward.

For example, in a workplace, it might be someone who decides who gets to attend certain meetings or have access to important documents, even though others could benefit from them. It's a way of keeping control over something that could be shared more freely.

As a learning designer I've faced marginalization, where I wasn't included in curriculum meetings or invited to contribute at a strategic level, even though my educational technology expertise was crucial.

To summarise these experiences, I wrote down more than a few of my colourful workplace stories and anecdotes. The presentation was starting to feel like a rambling outline for a twelve-episode Netflix drama. And it sounded a bit irritable. So instead of sharing these horror stories with you here today, I removed them from my presentation and copied them into ChatGPT with instructions to analyse. This revealed themes of marginalisation, misunderstanding, lack of collaboration, disrespect for expertise, unsustainable workloads, and power imbalances. The AI also provided recommendations: raising awareness of the role, clarifying responsibilities, creating structured collaboration, advocating for representation, and fostering professional development.

I've worked with lots of SMEs, both good and bad. I once got into a power struggle in a staff tearoom with an English teacher, all because poetry was in her teaching domain and supposedly not in mine. So, here is a poem.

The co-design path

(with apologies to Robert Frost)

In learning's craft, it's crystal clear,
No one builds it alone, my dear.
A team of pros, with wisdom wide,
Each plays their part with steady pride.

The SME, a guiding light,
Sharpens each lesson to fit just right.
From firefighters to surgeons skilled,
Their expertise our content fills.

To slice an onion, thin and sweet?
A chef's advice makes it complete.
But chickens, friends, I cannot charm—
I am not a chicken farmer!

For firefighting tactics bold,
Or legal cases tightly told,
A lawyer shares what they best know,
While scientists make learning grow.

Reputation risk? A school's top task—
Public relations experts we must ask.

In every field, I seek their hand,
To co-design and make it grand.

Beyond their knowledge, something more:
Trust and teamwork at the core.
Together we create what's best,
Respect and collaboration—our true test.

Conclusion

So, what am I working on right now, in terms of learning design? Well, I have a few casual roles happening, collaborating with some very pleasant SMEs. This suits me well. My recent role in facilitating online Live Sessions for the University of Technology, Sydney (UTS) in the Graduate Certificate in Learning Design (and its micro-credential equivalent) has been very constructivist and profoundly and professionally satisfying and enjoyable. My career is closer to its end than its beginning. Over the past 30 years as an educational resource developer, I've navigated diverse sectors and witnessed the evolving role of learning design. Even those less-than-optimal experiences have taught me some valuable lessons and provided me with some stories to tell. (I'm happy to share these, but not right now.) Whether called Instructional Designer, Educational Technologist, or Learning Experience Designer, the role remains crucial yet misunderstood. Systems that trust respect and recognise learning designers lead to better outcomes for everyone.

To close, I'll quote Dr. Norman Swan: "Work becomes oppressive when it feels relentless, unrecognized, badly managed, and the system doesn't allow you to do your best." My hope is that this presentation sparks further reflection and action to elevate the role of learning design.

Best wishes and farewell—see you in the evaluation phase.

Provocation

As with most provocations in academic contexts, this video is designed to challenge established ideas and spark critical debate. It's been developed to inform, entertain and push you out of your comfort zone, encourage you to think differently, reconsider your assumptions, and explore new perspectives.

3SS participants considered the video via the following prompts and a positive and constructive discussion ensued.

Discussion prompts

- Reflect on your own experiences in learning design, and as a "third space practitioner". Have you ever felt your role was invisible? How did you handle that?
- Think about systems or teams where learning designers are undervalued. What small changes could shift the perception?
- Share challenges and obstacles you've faced in co-designing with SMEs and how you overcame them.
- Share examples from your experience of positive collaborations with SMEs or other team members. What factors contributed to that success?

Reflection

November 2025

I'd like to offer a brief personal and professional reflection a year after the 3SS. Over the past 30 or so years, I've had an enjoyable career as a "producer of learning materials" or learning designer. (What's in a label? That which we call a "Learning Designer" by any other name would perform a similar set of tasks: the essence or value of something isn't necessarily altered by what we choose to call it.) Regarding the 3SS, I appreciated the opportunity to participate and share my thoughts, perspectives and learnings in the unexpected liminal "third space" of the 100% online "Slowposium". I'm advised that the 3SS was not intended as a research activity, yet I'm pleased the organising committee are able to document and disseminate the ideas presented by the contributors. Due to established protocols in the field, any participant comments or quotes in response to my presentation – also called "participant data" – cannot be used in the proceedings. This I understand and respect.

Central to my presentation (that is, apart from my professional identity and the Australian poultry production industry) is a fundamental idea around professional and collegial acknowledgement and the value of dialogue for professional growth, shared understanding, respect, trust and collaboration. My experience with 3SS was valuable. As a learning designer, I had a voice in this space. I felt acknowledged, seen and heard, especially when interacting with comments and responses in the online discussion forum that was associated with my presentation, reaching its full value with each forum post and reply, either from myself or from other participants who were enabled to speak and be heard. Messages sent and received.

My presentation yielded several responses and comments from others who attended the 3SS. (I'm unable to quantify this; it's enough to acknowledge a professional and collegial resonance with the ideas.) Further sharing my video presentation on additional social platforms – after the event, outside the 3SS Moodle site – attracted similar interest and discourse. (Again, these are outside the scope of the proceedings.)

In this collegial exchange and interchange, collective wisdom is realised. I look forward to reading the 3SS proceedings and continuing the conversation.

About the author

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